

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2

Sl. no.*	R	R ₁	M p.** °C	Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	232 ^b	80
2 ^a	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	255 ^c	85
3 ^a	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	197 ^c	82
4 ^a	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	259 ^b	75
5.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	94 ^d	95
6	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	91 ^d	76
7	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	235 ^b	82
8	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	246 ^b	85
9	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	230 ^b	73
10 ^a	<i>p</i> -COOC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	241 ^b	86
11.	<i>o</i> -NH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	228 ^b	81
12.	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	Br	265 ^e	65
13.	α -Naphthyl	H	239 ^b	79
14.	β -Naphthyl	H	246 ^b	80
15	Cyclohexyl	H	160 ^b	74
16	4-Phenylthiazol-2	H	294 ^b	62

* Compounds tested for antifungal and antibacterial activities. ** Crystallisation solvent: ^bchloroform, ^cbenzene, ^dDMSO, ^ebenzene+ethanol

TABLE 2 PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	M p °C	Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	215 ^b	73
2.	C ₇ H ₇	C ₆ H ₅	193 ^b	75
3.	C ₈ H ₉	C ₆ H ₅	120 ^f	73
R ₂ = R ₁				
4. ^a	Morpholine		189 ^b	69
5.	N-Phenylpiperazine		162 ^g	91

* Compounds tested for antifungal and antibacterial activities. ** Crystallisation solvent: ^bchloroform, ^cwater, ^dbenzene+ethanol

The ir spectra shows characteristic absorption bands at 3 400 br (NH), 1 720 (C=O of coumarin) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C=C ring stretch). It also exhibited an amide I band at 1 670–1 650 cm⁻¹ and amide II band at 1 560–1 540 cm⁻¹. Compound 3 (Table 2) did not exhibit the above bands, instead C=O absorption^g (of 3^o amide) was observed at 1 680–1 630 cm⁻¹. Pmr (90 MHz) spectra revealed the following: 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxyanilide (Table 1; 2, Sl. no. 1) δ (CDCl₃) 3.98 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.1–7.7 (m br, Ar) and 8.86 (1H, s, H-4); 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxy-(N-phenyl)anilide (Table 2; 3, Sl. no. 1) δ (CF₃COOH) 3.6 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.9–7.1 (m br, Ar), 8.0 (1H, s, 4-H).

Antifungal and antibacterial activity: Some selected compounds were tested for their antifungal and antibacterial activity in DMF and benzene solvents *in vitro* 8-Methoxycoumarin-3-carboxy-(*p*-bromo)anilide was found to be active against the fungi *Cryptococcus neoformans* (activity, 25 μ g ml⁻¹) and *Sporotrichum schenckii* (activity, 25 μ g ml⁻¹). 8-Methoxy-6-bromocoumarin-3-carboxy-*p*-bromo-anilide was active against the fungi *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (activity, 25 μ g ml⁻¹) and rest of the compounds were found to be inactive against the fungi. None of the compounds tested (MIC in

100 μ g ml⁻¹) was found to have antibacterial activity.

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Synthesis of 2-(3-Coumarinyl)-4(1H)-anthryridinones

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A survey of the literature revealed that very little work has been reported on the synthesis of anthryridines¹⁻³. In continuation of our work on the synthesis of anthryridines⁴, we report herein the synthesis of 2-(3-coumarinyl)-2(1H)anthryridinones (Scheme 1).

2-Amino-3-cyano-1,8-naphthyridine (1) was obtained by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde with malonitrile in ethanol with piperidine as catalyst⁵. Condensation of 1 with 3-acetylcoumarins (2) in glacial acetic acid with a catalytic amount of concentrated sulphuric acid resulted in the formation of 2-(3-coumarinyl)-4(1H)anthryridinones (3) in good yield. The structures of these compounds were in conformity with their elemental analyses and spectral (ir and mass) data. A comparison of the ir spectra of 3 with those of immediate

Scheme 1

precursors **1** and **2** was used as an indirect evidence for the structure elucidation of **3**. The ir spectra of **3** exhibited characteristic bands at 1 680 (C=O), 1 720 (lactonic C=O), 3 320 (NH) and an intense band at 1 600 (C=N), in addition to 1 460, 1 375, 1 230, 1 110, 1 025, 950, 870, 810 and 760 cm^{-1} . The absence of C≡N band at 2 200 cm^{-1} provided additional proof for the structural assignment of **3**. The mass spectra of **2** showed a strong molecular ion peak at m/z 371 which corresponds to the molecular formula $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$. The characterisation data of these compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4-(3-COUMARINYL)-4(1H)ANTHRYRIDINONES (3)*

R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
H	>800	60	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$
6-OCH ₃	>800	80	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$
7-OH	>800	66	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$
6-Cl	>800	80	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$
6-Br	>800	76	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Br}$
6,8-Di-Cl	>800	75	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_8\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2$
6,8-Di-Br	>800	74	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_8\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2$
6-NO ₂	>300	63	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$
8-NO ₂	>800	63	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$
8-OCH ₃ -6-NO ₂	>300	68	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$
6-Br-8-OCH ₃	>800	70	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{Br}$
5,6-Benzo	>800	68	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$

*C, H, N analyses satisfactory.

Experimental

M. ps. are uncorrected. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested by tlc. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer.

3-Acetylcoumarins (2): Various substituted-3-acetylcoumarins derived from salicylaldehydes and ethyl acetoacetate were prepared by the literature method⁶⁻⁸.

2-(3-Coumarinyl)-4(1H)naphthyridinones (3): A mixture of **1** (0.1 mol) and appropriate 3-acetyl

coumarin (**2**; 0.1 mol) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) in presence of a trace of concentrated H_2SO_4 for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured onto crushed ice and the separated solid filtered and recrystallised from aqueous acetic acid to give **3**.

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Substituted-1,8-naphthyridines. Part-VII. Synthesis and Biological Activity of 4-Arylazo-2-(1,8-naphthyridin-2-yl)phenols

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IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of substituted¹⁻⁴ and fused⁵⁻⁷ 1,8-naphthyridines, we report herein the synthesis of 4-arylazo-2-(1,8-naphthyridin-2-yl)phenols and evaluation of their biological activity. The reaction sequence is shown in Scheme 1.

The required 2-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1,8-naphthyridine¹ (**3**) was obtained by the Friedlander's condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (**1**) with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (**2**) in presence of ethanol containing a few drops of aqueous 20% KOH. The intermediate **3** on coupling with diazotised arylamines